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The Ethical Culture of a U.S. Research University in Transition: Understanding, and Working with, Undergraduate Curriculum Change in a Complex Pedagogical Community

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the development of mechanisms to understand, assess, and support a comprehensive reform of the general education curriculum at a major U.S. research university. In particular, we focus on how the university's ethical culture has been, and will be, influenced by the process of developing, implementing, and now working within this new educational framework, in which ethical reasoning is integrated across the general education curriculum. We employ the perspective of Asset-Based Community Development [ABCD], an established framework for identifying and mobilizing community resources for the benefit of its members. This approach is based on a pragmatic vision, focused on identifying key changes in skills and practices that result from the curriculum change process. By treating a university as a complex community in which we ourselves participate, rather than a more conventional corporate organization for example, we aim to understand and facilitate the development of a robust culture of STEM ethics. This involves questions at several levels regarding perceptions and involvement of faculty and administrators, the structure of larger social network(s) emerging from this initiative, as well as outcomes of students. We have developed a range of novel instruments to examine these issues, including surveys of faculty and student perceptions, perspectives, and competencies; interviews and focus groups; textual analysis of student competencies; and social network analysis. Data gathered in our analysis is being used as feedback to the curriculum change process, to help facilitate its implementation and foster the diffusion of an ethical climate for STEM practice.

1. BACKGROUND: THE PATHWAYS CURRICULUM

Virginia Tech (VT) is an institution in the process of profound transformations in its university-wide curriculum structure. In particular, the “Pathways to General Education” (or simply “Pathways”) curriculum aims to provide all undergraduate students with a meaningful program of study beyond their particular field of specialization. As defined by the Association of American Colleges and Universities (AAC&U), general education is “the part of a liberal education curriculum shared by all students. It provides broad exposure to multiple disciplines and forms the basis for developing important intellectual and civic capacities. General education can take many different forms.” Rolled out in Fall 2018, Pathways constitutes the first significant change made to the general education curriculum at Virginia Tech since 2002 and the first complete course-by-course overhaul since the university moved from quarters to semesters in 1985.

Among the most distinctive aspects of this plan is the mandatory integration of learning outcomes in either *ethical reasoning* or *intercultural and global awareness* (or both) into all general education program courses. These outcomes are defined as follows:

Ethical Reasoning Concept: Ethical Reasoning is the principled evaluation of moral and political beliefs and practices. Foundational learning of ethical theories, issues, and applications provides tools that enable students to deliberate and to assess for themselves claims about ethical issues in their personal, public, and professional lives. Courses addressing this outcome must meet a majority of the following learning outcomes: (1) Explain and contrast relevant ethical theories; (2) Identify ethical issues in a complex context; (3) Articulate and defend positions on ethical issues in a way that is both reasoned and informed by the complexities of those situations.

Intercultural and Global Awareness Concept: Intercultural and Global Awareness supports effective and appropriate interaction with a variety of people and different cultural contexts. Courses addressing this concept must meet a majority of the following learning outcomes: (1) Identify advantages and challenges of diversity and inclusion in communities and organizations; (2) Interpret an intercultural experience from both one’s own and another’s worldview; (3) Address significant global challenges and opportunities in the natural and human world.

In addition to the integrative component, students can choose from among three different options: (1) a traditional set of independent courses that combine to fulfill these requirements (known as the distributive model), (2) a structured “Pathways Minor” that pursues an interdisciplinary theme connecting 18+ credits of coursework, or (3) an independently designed “Alternative Pathway” unique to the needs of the individual student. The option generating the greatest excitement among faculty and students are the Pathways Minors. Unlike traditional minors, which consist of highly focused learning (e.g. Biology, Finance) often restricted to students from a particular college, Pathways minors are interdisciplinary by design, open to all undergraduates, and embed ethical and intercultural learning across the curriculum. Pathways minors include junior/senior level course-work that builds and integrates foundational learning, culminating in a capstone experience where students apply their learning through authentic projects, undergraduate research, study abroad, and/or service learning.

Pathways Minors explore big issues in STEM including (among others): *Pathways to Sustainability* which looks at sustainability practices from scientific, ethical, and sociocultural perspectives, *Data and Decisions* which offers opportunities for students to gain skills in gathering and analyzing data while examining societal impacts (e.g. use/misuse, bias), and *Global Food Security and Health* which combines courses on world hunger and modern agriculture with a study abroad experience to apply knowledge in Africa. These multi-course trajectories through general education, paired with the integrative concepts embedded across the program, provide students with repeated opportunities to engage ethics from multiple disciplinary perspectives, providing sustained opportunities for ethical reasoning development.

Our primary task in this project is to examine how the implementation of this new curricular strategy may foster a stronger “culture of STEM ethics” within the university, and what lessons might be transferable from observed successes in the process. As active participants in the curriculum reform, we also aim to facilitate this process of change by identifying approaches and resources that are proving most productive and disseminating them to relevant groups.

A key conceptual issue here is that the notion of a “culture of STEM ethics” is far from clear. A research university is, by any reasonable standard, a complex institution – combining multiple missions (education, research, outreach, etc.); employing, serving, even sometimes housing, entertaining, and feeding thousands of students, faculty, and staff; organized into dozens of independent departmental units under multiple collegiate or trans-collegiate affiliations; including individuals with diverse cultural, linguistic, geographic, and disciplinary backgrounds; and pursuing a spectrum of intellectual, social, and professional activities. As such, any *a priori* attempt to define the “culture” of a university is likely a vain pursuit, and limiting one’s attention to a “culture of ethics” or a “culture of STEM ethics” does little to simplify the task. We have thus approached this concern pragmatically, and rather than attempt to theorize formally about the constituent elements of culture, we have instead framed the problem through the following questions: (1) How does STEM ethics relate to general education in this case?; (2) Why and how might the Pathways approach prove specifically productive, based on established models for STEM pedagogy? (What to look for as plausible outcomes?); (3) How does one identify and conceptualize relevant elements of “university culture” that can be leveraged here?; and (4) How does the injection of cultural and ethical subjects into pedagogical practices feed back into the university environment to foster “ethical culture” more broadly? (How does increased focus on teaching and learning in this area translate into changes in individual and collective beliefs and practices?). The next section details the development of our conceptual framework for this study through these guiding issues.

2. A CONCEPTUAL FRAME FOR UNIVERSITY CULTURES OF ETHICS

At VT, the central ground of this academic transformation is the set of global-scale ethical considerations associated with developments in STEM. By moving from a model in which such issues are either absent from – or compartmentalized within – the undergraduate experience to one in which they are a ubiquitous element of general education, the university is promoting a culture of ethical STEM engagement that will prepare its graduates to contend more effectively with the complexities of the 21st Century intellectual landscape. To contextualize this realignment in the general

education framework, let us step back to consider some recent trends in higher education that centralize interdisciplinarity and – even more particularly – transdisciplinarity. For example, Frodeman and Mitcham [1] review the history of modern Western university education to highlight ongoing tensions between specialized disciplinary fields (particularly, but not exclusively, in emerging technical fields) and various boundary-crossing initiatives in both research and pedagogy. They emphasize that the record of the past century has shown a continuous trend toward ever narrower disciplinary demarcations across the university, and argue that this has led to a particular crisis in academia with epistemological, political, and metaphysical consequences. Confronted by issues whose scale, scope, and synthetic character cannot be addressed effectively by compartmentalized research methods, with public implications that demand sustainable results, accountability to social needs, and attention to human value concerns, the contemporary university is portrayed as needing fundamental changes. Frodeman and Mitcham describe these necessary shifts in terms of “broad, deep, and critical interdisciplinarity.” However, while some are geared towards work between disciplines (including proposals to investigate the dynamics of disciplinary formations themselves more closely), most might be more properly considered transdisciplinary as they are oriented towards the creation of more synthetic knowledge forms using multiple perspectives to understand increasingly complex phenomena. This critique of the status quo is congruent with a much broader body of literature on educational practice and reform (see, for example, [2,3]). Such analyses typically point to a small set of contemporary concerns about human sociotechnical systems, including globalization, technological change, sustainability of natural and built environments, and the intersection of facts and values (epistemology versus axiology). They also indicate specific roles for the arts, humanities, and social sciences in developing the tools to address such fundamentally human concerns.

In this context, a general education program designed to integrate ethical reasoning and intercultural awareness throughout the curriculum, with thematic minors fostering connections between multiple complementary fields on practical issues of common concern, has much to recommend it, in principle. The basic idea, which has recently been codified by the image of the “T-Shaped Student”, is not itself novel, but the best way to organize this to accomplish various desired outcomes remains in question. In our particular case, where the fundamental concern is how to cultivate a culture of STEM ethics among undergraduates at a major research university, there are a number of elements to consider. Most obviously, we might look for apparent learning gains in measurable ethical competencies among STEM majors, but this is really just the tip of the iceberg. The arguments for interdisciplinary reform described above would suggest, in addition, that instruction in culture and ethics may complement and mutually reinforce one another; that practice in viewing subjects synthetically and repeatedly from multiple perspectives may deepen appreciation of both relevant facts and relevant values; and that broader and deeper instruction in a range of humanistic, artistic, and social scientific subjects may be a positive end in itself in solving the problems of the future. As such, each of these elements may play its own role in contributing to the university’s culture of ethics. The tools we have developed to probe the effectiveness of the new curriculum are geared to capturing such contributions, and to identifying those pedagogical strategies and contexts that prove most productive in that regard.

A foundational argument of this project - advertised already above - is that the university is best viewed as a complex and multifaceted community. Here, we are responding to limitations in some common conceptions of ethical culture, in which approaches originating in the analysis of business organizations have taken center stage since the 1980s [4]. This dominant narrative, geared largely toward improvement of management and productivity, has been exported to other types of organizations with some difficulty. The study of universities, for example, has been a conspicuous case where insights from organizational management have proven limited. Kuh & Whitt [5] detailed a far richer vision of university culture, drawing upon sociological and anthropological resources to highlight the multiplicity of roles, goals, and subcultures that more typically characterize a university. More recently, Harold Silver [6] has gone even further to suggest that the conception of “university culture” presupposes a level of cohesiveness that may not exist at all. Such critiques of the notion of “university culture” as either structured or unitary underpin our approach.

Fortunately, per Frodeman and Mitcham’s observations above, the humanities and social sciences provide ample other resources to characterize culture – and to situate ethical concerns within culture. Returning to such perspectives in this discussion is useful here for two reasons: The sociological-anthropological approach to culture brings in features that critics note as absent from the organizational literature. These same resources, we note, are central to the general education strategy under investigation in our case. In particular, we wish to highlight some key features beyond organizational typology, including a vision of culture as pluralistic, multifaceted, and dynamically evolving. Individuals and groups participate in multiple cultures, sometimes conflicting with or overlapping one another. Cultures, in addition, exceed their contractual, formal, or structural elements, and also include resources to develop, connect, and reflect – such as symbolic acts, communal activities, a sense of purpose, and space and time.

Ultimately, we contend that, studying a university culture of ethics is simply a special case of studying a large and diverse community and its values. Our particular study aims to characterize not just a university culture of ethics, but the effect of a major transition in general education on such a culture. This process, amounts to a new and systematic focus on axiological education – aiming to develop skills in the understanding of values in general, with ethics as a subset, and STEM ethics as a subset of that. Here, importantly, the features of the new curriculum structure itself are designed to integrate ethical reasoning and intercultural awareness into the entire undergraduate general education program, using the same conceptual approaches just introduced to create a broad interdisciplinary context for education in ethics and culture. In other words, the transition under study injects the subject of culture itself into the university culture in a concentrated way.

3. METHODS

The activities of this project will be geared toward a systematic analysis of developments in the culture of STEM ethics at VT as the new Pathways curriculum is implemented, and the potential transferability or collaborative extension of successful strategies to other sites. This analysis will involve qualitative and quantitative data collection to assess several interrelated outcomes of the transformation process: (1) the efficacy of the new programs themselves; (2) the dynamics of the individual,

collective, and institutional processes evident in their implementation; and (3) the overall utility of the theory of change employed in implementing Pathways.

Since this project explores the institutional ethical STEM culture, all 29,000 undergraduate students enrolled and over 1500 faculty working at Virginia Tech are eligible to participate. However, a specific focus will be placed on those students who have entered since Fall 2018 when the new general education program was implemented, approximately 13,000 students. Although every student is required to complete the program by the time they graduate, to date over 400 students have pursued a Pathways Minor as means to complete a portion of those requirements, which will serve as a particular point of inquiry. Since the period of study also affords us the opportunity to compare the outcomes of students whose undergraduate experience (partially or completely) predates the implementation of the new system, we are also including a longitudinal (pre-post) component in the analysis of student surveys.

3.1 Student surveys

We plan to investigate the development of student ethical competence through analysis of secondary data such as student assignments and conduct of surveys of students in Pathways courses and elsewhere. We intend to compare outcomes between students who enrolled in the Pathways minors and those who did not. We will further examine learning through proxy indicators developed based upon conscientious review of faculty reports of teaching in the Pathways program. We will survey students within Pathways courses and students who are not enrolled in Pathways courses. We will engage in a targeted recruitment strategy to ensure that we have adequate numbers of students in ethics-only, ethics and global awareness, and non-ethics focused Pathways courses in order to conduct between group analysis of their responses. We will use a closed survey protocol with no open-ended answers as we expect that the pertinent content of open-ended answers will be reflected in artifacts from student assignments. Our survey questions will use a combination of Likert-type responses, dichotomous (like/dislike), marked semantic differentiations. Students enrolled in Pathways courses will be surveyed at the beginning of their courses and at the end in order to assess any differences in response. Through coordination with the Office of General Education and relevant academic departments, we will endeavor to re-survey students who took an ethics-focused pathways course one academic year after the completion of their course to test for durable effects.

3.2 Faculty surveys and interviews

We will explore faculty perceptions about their ethical teaching competence using a combination of narrative interviews and participant observation of courses. Interviews will investigate faculty perceptions, concerns, and challenges related to implementation of ethics in their courses. Second, based on data gathered in this phase, we will work within existing faculty communities and training programs to develop and offer specific faculty ethics education opportunities and resources. These will likely include a faculty development summer institute, workshops, and course redesign opportunities. We are currently conducting semi-structured interviews with faculty currently teaching in the Pathways program who have and have not completed the Pathways Summer Institute as well as faculty who are teaching non Pathways affiliated courses that are part of the VT general education curriculum. We expect to find differences between the three groups' perceptions of the meaning of ethics

teaching and challenges associated with incorporating ethical perspectives into their courses. We also expect to find variation in the course assessment mechanisms used by instructors of ethics-focused courses and courses without an ethics focus. Sample questions span these three areas of concern-- perceptions, challenges, and variations-- and include examples such as, "Before you began working with the Pathways program, what was your perception of ethics teaching in a collegiate classroom? Has that perception changed since you have been teaching your course? How has your perception changed?". We are audio recording each of the interviews, will have each directly transcribed, and will use Computer Aided Content Analysis to identify emergent and consistent themes throughout the interviewee's descriptions. We will use standard sentiment analysis techniques on the varieties of ethical speech to determine what perceptions, challenges and variations the three groups of faculty have of ethics material in STEM courses.

To investigate what are the transferable lessons learned from this project including elements applicable to, or adopted by other institutions [Propagating Transferable Elements] we will characterize faculty and students' role as change agents in university culture. The structure of the new curriculum, featuring developmental course sequences and cross/inter-disciplinary interactions, and with faculty participating in more cross-disciplinary teaching, make it likely that both faculty and students will experience changes in the skill sets they require over time. For example, as students' level of ethics understanding increases, we expect that they will seek new and different opportunities for meaningful learning in their courses, and as faculty engage in more cross-disciplinary teaching, they will make different demands on university systems (e.g., library programs). Determination of how changes in student and faculty cultures lead to changes in university administrative support structures will be a novel contribution of this project.

3.3 Social Network Analysis

Social network analysis (SNA) [7] will be applied as a tool to both measure progress and guide the next steps of ABCD to build a community improving STEM learning at VT and other schools. Because there is limited empirical evidence documenting the impact of ABCD on community development [8] and ABCD has not been applied previously to university transformation, this research will contribute new knowledge for the fields of STEM education and more broadly, institutional change theories. For our project, the social network is defined as the individuals and units (actors) linked to the general education reform process. Connections between actors are made where there are collaborations and relationships. As the steps of ABCD are applied, the social networks will be analyzed to measure growth and strengthening of the community [9] and to identify emerging leadership opportunities (actors with many ties). Both quantitative (surveys and network analytics) and qualitative (interviews and focus groups) methods will inform the construction and analysis of social networks. These methods will also provide data about what network members are doing to improve STEM learning and the extent to which participation in the communities influences and supports this work.

4. Asset-Based Community Development & Agents of Change

Virginia Tech is engaging in a university-wide general education reform project as a means to infuse a culture of STEM ethics by integrating ethics education as a cross-

cutting outcome, with extended learning experiences through the Pathways Minors. Culture changes in higher education institutions require successful use of multiple change strategies at multiple levels; many change efforts fail because change agents do not realize the need to activate these different strategies, as documented by Henderson, Beach, and Finkelstein [10]. In addition, as Kezar [11] outlines, a change agent must have a variety of institutional change theories (e.g. social, scientific, etc.) in their toolbox to utilize on a case-by-case basis throughout the reform effort. To reign in this potential spiralling complexity, a framework is needed that is both clear and simple enough to guide the change agents at each step of the process and flexible enough to allow for the deployment of varied change strategies along the way.

The VT curriculum reform process has been explicitly guided by an Asset-Based Community Development (ABCD) theory of change [12]. ABCD provides change agents with a positive strategy for transformation that focuses on community members' diverse strengths and seeks to engage all stakeholders in the change process, centered within the context of the unique institution. This strengths-based focus contrasts with organizational change theories utilized to address a singular stakeholder deficit (e.g. 'students are underprepared for the course' or 'instructors are ill-equipped to provide engaging learning opportunities in large classes'), as a response to an external pressure or peer competition (e.g. 'the state requires more global focus in the curriculum' or 'a peer institution has created a center to address that research gap so we should too'), or within a clearly structured power hierarchy (e.g. 'the CEO wants the company to expand into a new market so the whole company follows') [11]. Because a general education reform is complex (incorporating all of the issues above and more), ever-evolving, institution-specific, politically-charged (internally and externally), and requires multiple change theories and initiatives operating simultaneously, ABCD is an appropriate framework to guide complex change.

In addition, in ABCD lasting positive change is built upon a widely held recognition that each individual possesses assets (e.g., talents in teaching, disciplinary knowledge, leadership skills) to contribute to ongoing community development. Stakeholders are citizens in the community, not clients buying a product [13], so phrases like 'faculty buy-in' or 'resistance to accepting change' are not as applicable in this framework. ABCD guides strategy for building and assessing networks of faculty, students, and community members committed to improving and infusing a campus ethics culture. This approach has been effective in facilitating change in social work and community development, but has not yet been applied to the university at this scale.

ABCD is a 5-step framework: 1) map the assets, 2) build relationships, 3) mobilize the assets, 4) convene a broadly representative group, and 5) leverage the resources. In step 1, a proper asset mapping inventory elucidates physical, individual, associational, and institutional assets that can contribute to the desired community development. In this case, the long-time chair of a curriculum committee can bring historical knowledge and lessons learned while the Registrar's Office has access to policies and procedures that align with the change efforts. In step 2, a great deal of time and effort is spent on building relationships among the community members. At Virginia Tech, stakeholders like curriculum committees, advising personnel, and community partners are brought together through matchmaking, networking, and joint professional development events. To mobilize the assets in step 3, a general education website (common resource repository) is constructed, an awards reception is held, and a grants program

is offered to bring recognition and financial support to community members. In step 4, change facilitators bring the community together to develop a unified plan of action, in this case new policies, procedures, and structures to support the general education community broadly. Finally, in step 5, both internal (budgets, faculty lines) and external resources (e.g. NSF grants and community partnerships) are leveraged to expand the successful components and fill the financial gaps.

Change agents rely on ABCD for the framework and mindset in which to operate. In the context of general education reform, university administrators assume the role of facilitators ('mobility agents' in ABCD terminology) who identify community assets and provide opportunities for relationship-building and asset mobilization to foster ongoing improvement and create widespread engagement in building a culture of ethical STEM. The administrators facilitating the general education transition have researched, attended workshops on, presented workshops on, and modified and built on the tools provided by ABCD literature and professional development support [12]. As the project progresses, training would expand to mobility agents beyond central administration.

The role of the mobility agent is "to support networks that foster mutual learning and shared commitments so that people can work... together in relatively coherent and equitable communities." [7] At all stages, but particularly during the 'building relationships' and 'mobilizing the assets' stages, the mobility agent helps members build social and trust capital through support provided and connections made. Without trust, change leaders cannot progress through the steps of community development, thus sustainable long-term culture construction and change cannot be achieved.

By addressing all four domain areas in Henderson et al.'s [10] change strategy schema - changing curriculum and pedagogy; offering faculty development opportunities; making concordant policy; and developing a shared vision (in this case for ethics education across the university) -- and guided by an ABCD framework, mobility agents can cultivate and infuse a campus culture of ethical STEM.

5) Conclusions

Virginia Tech is undergoing a major transformation of their general education curriculum, infusing both ethical reasoning and intercultural and global awareness into each Pathways course. Pathways look to explore the intersection between scientific, ethical, and sociological perspectives and apply these various frames to interrelated societal contexts, providing students with a broad yet interconnected experience, partially motivated by an increasingly siloed and disciplinary higher education environment. This project looks to evaluate the university's ethical culture as it goes through this transition while also looking to ascertain the impact of an integrated general education curriculum has on this community of scholars. To measure this cultural shift, this project will utilize a variety of methods to determine perceptions of various participant groups throughout the university-wide change. The project utilizes surveys of both faculty and students, interviews of faculty and staff, textual analysis of student assignments, and social network analysis in a holistic attempt to map the existing networks and assets of individuals and departments across Virginia Tech. In alignment with both the goals of the institution and the proposed ABCD model for change this project seeks to measure the ethical climate and facilitate sustaining cultural change at Virginia Tech.

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